

STATE POLICY FOR YOUTH

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Annotation: *The role of young people as a driving force for the stability of society in the world, the issues of their social adaptation to society, the general policy of young people in different countries is one of the most pressing issues today. This article also discusses the state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *patriotism, initiative, broad reforms, laws, youth rights, intellectual potential;*

INTRODUCTION

It should be noted that educating young people in the country in the spirit of patriotism, respect for national traditions and values, raising a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation, protecting their rights and interests, as well as comprehensively developed, independent-minded, Particular attention is paid to creating a solid legal basis for the education of enterprising young people who are able to take responsibility for their future, who are mobilized in the interests of the people, and who are able to realize their intellectual and creative potential.

DISCUSSION

In order to radically improve the work in this area and raise it to a new level of quality and to ensure the full implementation of the tasks set out in the Law "On State Youth Policy", effective cooperation in this area is carried out by public authorities, NGOs and other civil society institutions. It is important to increase. It should be noted that, given the current needs and requirements, special attention has been paid to the problems of young people in our country, and a wide range of opportunities has been created to meet their interests and needs, that is, representatives from state and public organizations directly responsible for youth issues have been appointed, and extensive reforms have been made in this regard. In particular, the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Deputy Governors of regions, Tashkent, districts and cities for youth policy, social development and spiritual and educational work, positions in charge of youth issues in educational institutions, as well as 2022 Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-92 of January 19, 2013 "On measures to radically improve the system of work with youth in the neighborhoods" The fact that the rights and interests of our youth are protected by public organizations on the basis of mutual cooperation, as provided by the relevant laws, is a clear proof of our words.

The state youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the following rules:

- care for young people, regardless of nationality, race, language, religion, social status, gender, education and political beliefs;
- legal and social protection of youth;
- The transmission of national and cultural traditions from generation to generation, the spiritual connection of generations;
- support youth initiatives, ensure that young people are free to choose the path of their interests in accordance with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- direct participation of youth in the development and implementation of policies and programs for the development of society, especially in the life of the youth of the republic;
- ensuring the unity of rights and duties, freedoms and civic responsibilities.

According to the above rules, the state policy on youth is constantly improving its content, constantly focusing on the most complex aspects of public life.

The main principles of the state policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at the younger generation are constantly evolving, enriching their content and showing their internal momentum. As a result, the following tasks have been set in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the implementation of state youth policy:

- determination of socio-economic, legal and organizational bases of the state youth policy in the territory of the republic;
- development and provision of measures for social protection of youth;
- Establishment of government agencies for youth policy;
- Development and implementation of comprehensive and targeted programs in the field of state youth policy in the Republic;
- Management of financial resources for the implementation of state youth policy;
- to represent the interests of the youth of the republic in the framework of Uzbekistan's international obligations;
- Legal regulation of social relations of youth and their associations in the territory of the republic;
- Socio-economic, political, legal and external support of the initiatives of the youth of the republic, youth public associations;
- control over the observance of the obligations of all legal entities to the youth established by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, other issues of formation and implementation of youth policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

On the basis of the above-mentioned tasks, the country has been consistently implementing long-term programs for the gradual, goal-oriented reform of the education system.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation has been identified by the head of our state as a top priority for the country. Their strength and potential are reflected in the mobilization of the country for peace, development and prosperity of the people.

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